

Communication in the Education of Wife Teacher Girls the Place of Culture

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Abstract: This article examines the communication culture of women teachers and students and the impact of culture on communication, and comments on how pedagogues can create a more effective learning environment by adopting the culture of communication.

Keywords: communication, culture, education, pedagogue, rebuke, courtesy, knowledge, skill, competence, didactics, assessment, volition, purity, cooperation.

Communication is a process of exchange of information between people. There are different definitions of the concept. Communication information of a cognitive or affective nature between two or more people in exchange as their interaction is defined. Communication IS a complex process of establishing and developing relationships arising from the need for cooperation between people and consisting of information exchange, development of a single way of interaction, perception and understanding of another person, comprehensive process.

Communication culture can be formed from youth in the family, under the influence of the social environment, as a result of self-awareness and upbringing. In this, adults should be an example for young people. By imitating the communication of adults, the art of communication and culture is formed in them. In educational institutions, pedagogues, especially female pedagogues, should take into account the age, gender, and worldview of students in forming students' communication. It is of great importance that female teachers, based on their skills, use communication methods based on the temperament characteristics of students. The role of communication in students' formation of knowledge, skills, and abilities is incomparable. We have set before us to educate a fully developed, mature, perfect person (person). The President always likes to educate young people to think freely. So, communication is formed in an integral connection with thinking.

In the educational system, the communication culture of women pedagogues, how they communicate with students and how they teach, play an important role in everyday life. Women teachers in their professional activities not only teach scientific knowledge, but also influence students from social, moral and psychological aspects. Their communication culture plays a key role in ensuring the effectiveness of the educational process, personal development of students, and overall positive educational environment.

In the modern education system, the interaction of women pedagogues with students, establishing proper communication with them, understanding their needs and providing them with appropriate education is of great importance. Female educators can successfully manage the educational process by following humaneness, sincerity, respect, caution and high moral values in their work. This style of communication not only shapes students' reading skills, but also their personal qualities.

Also, the communication culture of female pedagogues should be established not only with students, but

also with parents, management bodies and other pedagogues. At a time when the importance of teamwork is increasing in the educational system, the good communication culture of women educators is important for effective teamwork and achieving common goals in education.

At the same time, it is necessary to take into account several factors for the development of communication culture of female pedagogues. Their professional training, communication skills, knowledge in the field of pedagogical psychology, and the ability to use modern educational technologies increase the effectiveness of the educational process.

Acquiring communication culture is important for pedagogues, especially for female pedagogues. Because the work of a pedagogue always requires communicating with students, interacting with each other. It educates students through the communication process, has a pedagogical effect, forms a scientific worldview, high faith in them, and inculcates positive moral qualities. Any pedagogue who has started his teaching career should master the culture of communication, be able to freely express his opinion to others, and become specialists who can speak in purely literary language. Therefore, education of pedagogical communication among female pedagogues should be an integral part of the educational system in pedagogical institutes, one of the most important tasks. Pedagogical dialogue is a dialogue between a teacher and students, in the process of which, thanks to the exchange of information, the pedagogue gives knowledge to students, has an educational effect on them, and achieves mutual understanding and perception. . A pedagogue can achieve his goal only if he can properly organize cooperation with students in the pedagogical process, that is, he can establish interaction and mutual understanding in accordance with the goals and tasks of education. For this purpose, the future teacher must have thoroughly mastered the requirements for the culture of pedagogical communication and its laws.

When determining the communication culture, we should know the following.

General norms. In this case, the values and beliefs that govern the communication within a certain group represent the relationship between the teacher and the student.

Communication styles. The way teachers and students communicate, including verbal and nonverbal communication, affects teacher-student interactions.

Communication culture plays an extremely important role in the pedagogical activity of pedagogues, that is, a pedagogue who has a culture of communication does not have misunderstandings in his activities with students. In the process of communication, it is necessary to take into account their individual characteristics, demands and suggestions, especially female teachers and girls, should use verbal and non-verbal communication appropriately. As a result, mutual respect, mutual understanding and trust between the pedagogue and students.

The following strategies play an important role for effective communication between the teacher and students.

Active listening. It is necessary to pay close attention to the students' words for proper understanding. Pupils also want teachers to listen. Because he wants to convey his thoughts, thoughts, feelings to the teacher through his words. When the teacher listens to the students, the student begins to admit that they have some level of self-respect. Being attentive to the information being transmitted is a sign of being aware of conflicts. It is necessary to try to listen to the student's words with patience and satisfaction.

Clear communication. Use clear and concise language, avoiding jargon or complex vocabulary words unfamiliar to students.

Ask questions. Educators should encourage students to ask questions and engage in open dialogue to clarify information or express their views. But open and clear questions - what?! Open and clear questions are questions that do not use the words "yes" or "no" as an answer, can be a broad answer, and can be fully answered by the student in all aspects of the study.

Because the teacher should get a lot of information about the student from him. At the same time, the teacher helps him to get out the thoughts that are bothering him by asking open and clear questions. By asking such questions, the student is satisfied that his problems are not indifferent to the teacher, that the teacher is paying attention to his personality and words.

Educators should actively listen and empathize with students when communicating with them. This leads to deeper understanding as a result of listening carefully to students. Pay attention to the student's words, tone of voice and body language.

The teacher should show empathy towards students and try to understand the student's point of view and feelings, recognize their feelings and show empathy. Then there will be mutual respect, open communication and empathy between the pedagogue and students.

So, communication is a very complex and multifaceted process, which is studied by representatives of various disciplines - philosophers, sociologists, cultural scientists, psychologists and linguists. Philosophers study the place of communication in the life of a person and society, its role in human development. Sociologists study the forms of communication between different social groups and groups, the differences in the types of communication related to social causes. Psychologists consider both the form of activity and human behavior, individual psychotypical characteristics of communication, as well as the place of communication in the structure of individual consciousness. Cultural scientists establish relationships between types of culture and forms of communication. Linguists study the linguistic and discourse nature of social and interpersonal communication.

Thus, the communication culture of female pedagogues in education is important not only in communication with students, but also in ensuring the quality of the entire educational environment. This factor increases the effectiveness of education and serves as a solid foundation for preparing students for life.

In conclusion, in the conditions of modern society, it is of great importance for pedagogues to master the culture of communication.

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